

An Unusual Mechanism of Small Bowel Obstruction: Entrapment of Meckel's Diverticulum Through an Adhesive Bridge

Author: Abdallah Shurrab¹

Co-authors: Mouaiad Abu Alika¹

Coordinator: Cristian Bulat²

Affiliations:

¹ *Grigore T. Popa University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iasi, Romania*

² *Department of General Surgery, Emergency County Hospital "St. Spiridon" Iasi, Romania*

Introduction

Meckel's diverticulum (MD) is the most common congenital anomaly of the gastrointestinal tract. While complications such as bleeding, inflammation, and obstruction are well described, the latter is typically attributed to mesodiverticular bands, volvulus, or intussusception. Internal herniation and entrapment of the diverticulum itself through an ileal-mesenteric adhesive bridge represents an exceptionally rare and poorly documented mechanism of small bowel obstruction (SBO).

Case Presentation

A 42-year-old male presented to the emergency department with diffuse abdominal pain, progressive distension, nausea, and vomiting, without a history of prior abdominal surgery. Clinical examination and imaging studies (including abdominal X-ray, ultrasonography, and abdominopelvic computed tomography) were consistent with SBO. Exploratory laparotomy revealed a fibrous adhesive bridge tethering an ileal segment to the adjacent mesentery, forming a constricting orifice. A Meckel's diverticulum was found internally herniated through this orifice and entrapped at its base, with associated obstruction and ischemia of the adjacent ileal segment. Adhesiolysis was performed followed by diverticulectomy. Because the adjacent bowel was ultimately viable, segmental resection was not required. No post-operative complications occurred. Hence, the patient was discharged later. Histopathological examination confirmed MD with areas of gastric metaplasia.

Conclusion

Most reported cases of MD-related obstruction involve the diverticulum forming a band or acting as a lead point. In contrast, this case illustrates an unusual mechanism in which the diverticulum itself became the entrapped structure. This rare presentation expands the spectrum of MD-related obstruction and highlights an extraordinary obstructive mechanism that may be difficult to anticipate preoperatively. Recognition of this mechanism is essential, particularly in patients with SBO without prior abdominal surgery. Increased awareness may facilitate timely surgical intervention, prevent ischemic complications, and address a significant gap in the current literature.

Keywords

Meckel's diverticulum, Small bowel obstruction, Internal herniation, Adhesion, Adhesive band